

TREASURE

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Training of Early Stage Researchers: a Pilot Study**

Reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices and outputs list

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Contributors: Ana dos Santos Carvalho, Bruno Direito, Catarina Domingues, Elsa Henriques, Fernando V. Borges, Inês A. T. Almeida, João Ramalho-Santos, Jorge Noro, Maria João Neves, Paulo J. Oliveira, Tracey L. Weissgerber, Ana Teixeira, Carmen Soares, Carolina Cabaços, Cláudia Cavadas, Gonçalo Santos, Henrique Girão, Isabel V. Figueiredo, João Gabriel Silva, João Peça, Jorge Varanda, Liliana Baptista, Lucas Belo, Luís C. Dias, Luiza Franco, Marco Pereira, Maria Cohen, Maria João Antunes, Maria Manuel Borges, Mariana Linharelhos, Nuno Empadinhas, Paulo Pinheiro, Pedro A. Santos, Sabrina Pereira, Sofia Wasterlain, Bruno Béu, Matthew Lucas, Miriam Kip, Natalie C. Evans, Tamarinde Haven

Reviewed and authorized: Vice-rector for Research, João Ramalho-Santos (Coordinator)

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*This document includes the **reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs**, and the **assessment criteria** that will be used to check and assess the implementation of these practices within 2nd and 3rd cycle dissertations/theses, both high-level criteria (across practices & disciplines) and operationalization criteria (at the practice level & considering field-specifications).*

*This is a **provisional version** to be updated in the deliverable D.2 report.*

Document structure

1. Introduction

- a. Aims
- b. Explanation of terminologies used
- c. Overview of the practices included in the list
- d. High-level assessment criteria
- e. Operationalization criteria

2. Practices + Criteria

- a. Denomination of practice
 - (i) What is it (What is not)
 - (ii) Why is it important
 - (iii) Examples

3. Practices that were considered but are not in the list

- a. Denomination of practice

Introduction

AIMS

The aim of this document is to provide a range of reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices & outputs from which the students can select. When choosing the practices to implement in their own research, master and doctoral candidates should consider:

- Which practices and outputs **best fit** their research project and each study in particular (e.g., if a thesis has 3 different studies, some practices may apply to some studies and not to others, or the student may want to select different RROR practices for each study)
- Whether any of the following **restrictions** apply to the thesis/dissertation research project and/or any of its studies, limiting student's ability to openly share some of the products (e.g., methods, step-by-step protocols, materials, data):
 - **Sensitive/personal** (e.g., data protection; informed consent; data sovereignty)
 - **Intellectual property** rights – industrial (including patents, trademark, trade secrets) & copyright
 - **National security** (e.g., intelligence data)

Students should consult their supervisors, institutional ethical committees, and other relevant instances to know the legal and institutional regulations in place and if restrictions apply. When restrictions prohibit sharing of some outputs, students should consider whether they are still able to implement other practices, which may include sharing outputs that are not subject to restrictions.

RROR PRACTICES & OUTPUTS LIST

Overview of the practices included in the list

1. Author contribution statements [\[practice\]](#)
2. Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps [\[practice\]](#)
3. Preregistration or Study design plans [\[output\]](#)
4. Registered Reports [\[output\]](#)
5. Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies [\[practice\]](#)
6. Open step-by-step methods and protocols [\[output\]](#)
7. Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science or Participatory research [\[practice\]](#)
8. Open/reusable materials/resources [\[output\]](#)
9. Unique and Persistent Identifiers for research materials/resources [\[practice\]](#)
10. Open source code and software [\[output\]](#)
11. Open source hardware [\[output\]](#)
12. Open benchmarking of problems [\[output\]](#)
13. Data sharing [\[output\]](#)
14. Following Reporting guidelines [\[practice\]](#)
15. Preprints [\[output\]](#)

- 16. Reporting of null results [\[output\]](#)
- 17. Science communication, dissemination, and policy recommendations [\[practice\]](#)
- 18. Open educational materials [\[output\]](#)

CRITERIA

High-level assessment criteria (*applied to all practices and outputs, irrespective of field of knowledge*):

- **Presence and findability: Practices** that can be implemented in a research paper (e.g., author contributions statements, following reporting guidelines, or using globally unique and persistent identifiers) must be **visibly implemented (i.e., reported) in the thesis**. When a **separate output** is created and shared on a public or restricted access repository, this **output must be cited in the thesis**. Examples might include preregistrations, open reusable step-by-step protocols, or open data. The citation must allow readers to find the output.
- **Quality assessment: The practice/output should be assessed based on quality**. We would prefer that students implement a few practices/outputs very well, instead of implementing many practices/outputs poorly.
- **FAIRness:** When **outputs** are shared on repositories, the **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) **principles** should be applied whenever possible, by implementing two essential and one important points defined by the Research Data Alliance Maturity model (FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group2020, <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>):
 - The output should have associated high quality, rich, **metadata** (context, description, etc.) ([FAIR principle F2](#))
 - The output should have assigned a **globally unique and persistent identifier**, such as a DOI or a handle ([FAIR principle F1](#))
 - The output should be associated with a clear standard reuse, preferentially an open research friendly, **license**, e.g., if using Creative Commons: CC0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA; GNU; etc.) ([FAIR principle R1.1](#)). If a material or output is published without license attribution, full copyright is assumed to be retained by the author, despite being publicly available (source: [University of Cambridge](#)).
- **Contributor roles:** for all **outputs** resulting from the thesis, an Author contributions statement should specify the contributions of all contributors, not just the student.

Operationalization criteria (*defined at the practice level, and with field specifications*):

- How will **quality** be assessed:
 - At the **practice** level (*i.e., what should be generally included in the practice, considering the rationale behind the practice recommendation to improve science, research and scholarship – what does it try to promote/prevent, and if minimum standards to achieve this were reached*)
 - At the **discipline** level (*e.g., are there standards for the field and, if so, were they followed, etc.*)

EXPLANATIONS OF TERMINOLOGY USED

Throughout this guide we use terminologies in their broader meaning as simplifications of more concrete concepts or terms:

- **Research:** we use “research” as an umbrella term of broad meaning to refer to both science (and disciplines using the scientific method), research and scholarship, therefore including fields such as natural sciences, health sciences, social sciences, arts and humanities, technology, engineering and mathematics;
- **Thesis:** we use “Thesis” to refer both to master *dissertations* and doctoral *thesis*; as well as *final activity report* that may be presented in lieu of a thesis for conclusion of master degree in some programs;
- **Practice:** by research “practice or practices” we refer to a methodology or collection of methodologies used to produce, to report or to disseminate research outputs. Practices can be reproduced or replicated (different sample);
- **Output:** by research “output” we refer to the product of one or more research practices (not necessarily included in this document) that has a [Uniform Resource Identifier \(URI\)](#) and can be accessible in a repository;
- **Field:** By “field” we mean field of knowledge, or discipline, in its broader meaning (such as the broad and second-level areas defined in the Frascati Manual, 2015) or in its more specific meaning if concerning specific disciplinary communities within field. The term “discipline” may be used interchangeably;
- **Metadata:** all the additional information that provides context and describes the characteristics, properties, and attributes of data, including information that is necessary for understanding and correctly using the raw data within a given context or domain (Cunha-Oliveira et al, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00043.2023>). In the current document, the concept of metadata is extended beyond “data” to include all types of research outputs that require additional information to be properly interpreted either by humans or machines;
- **Globally unique identifier:** a compact sequence of characters used to identify an entity (i.e. an identifiable unit of digital or physical type that can be found in a database, registry, repository, ontology, etc), not only locally (within a database or source) but across contexts (source: McMurry et al, 2017). See also Uniform Resource Identifier.
- **Persistent identifier:** «a long-lasting reference to a document, file, web page, or other object. The term "persistent identifier" is usually used in the context of digital objects that are accessible over the Internet» (source: [Wikipedia](#))
- **Uniform Resource Identifier (URI):** An identifier (compact sequence of characters) that is guaranteed to be both uniform and globally unique, identifying an abstract or physical resource (source: The Internet Society, 2005, <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc3986>; McMurry et al., 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>, Supplementary Information Table 1)
- **License:** Licenses define if and how others can use, modify, and share creative work (source: Konkol, [personal communication](#)). Some licenses are more appropriate for some types of creative work (e.g., Creative Commons licenses are not recommended for computer software or

hardware), and should not be applied to works that are no longer under copyright or that are already in the public domain (source: [Creative Commons](#)).

REPRODUCIBLE, REUSABLE AND OPEN RESEARCH (RROR) PRACTICES LIST AND ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

To be included in the list, practices should:

- 1) aim to improve the **reproducibility, reusability and openness of research (RROR)**
- 2) be **assessable in a graduate student thesis** (e.g., a peer-reviewed open access research article may not be published before dissertation/thesis finalization)
- 3) be a practice or output **that a graduate student might create** (e.g., Ethics approval is not the student's responsibility)

Note: Some of the practices on the list may already be widely performed in specific fields. We may address this by weighing criteria at later stages, as the goal of the program is to go beyond what is already standard practice within a field.

1. Author Contribution Statements

What: Author Contribution Statements are statements that specify the tasks that each author or contributor completed during the research. Author contributions statements can be included in the thesis, in research papers, or in other research outputs that are deposited on repositories (e.g., pre-registrations, study design protocols, data, code). The number and order of authors may differ on different outputs. The author contributions statement should help readers to understand the reasons for these differences. For example, a researcher who wrote the code for the analysis may be the first author on the repository containing that code but may be a middle author on the paper. Compared to the final paper, a pre-registered study plan may include a smaller number of authors who conceptualized and designed the study.

This statement may follow the CRediT taxonomy (*Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing*), or specify specific contributions without using a taxonomy, as long as it clearly specifies the tasks performed by each author. Some journals specifically require CRediT author contributions statements, whereas others allow authors to determine how author contributions statements are reported.

Why:

- Provides a clear public statement of what tasks each researcher performed when completing the study.
- Researchers can receive credit for the different outputs that they created or helped to create during their research, demonstrating their expertise and roles in producing each output, and building an assessable portfolio to showcase different skills.
- Early career researchers can use author contributions statements to show potential employers what they have done.

Examples - What might this look like?

General:
Contributor Roles Taxonomy, CRediT, https://credit.niso.org Other - General approach: Emily Davis devised the project, the main conceptual ideas, proof outline, and wrote the manuscript. Michael Smith worked on all of the technical details and performed the numerical calculations for the suggested experiment. Robert Snow worked out the bound for quantum experiments and verified the results. (source: https://www.cwauthors.com/article/Drafting-Authorship-Contribution-Statement)
Field specific examples:
Architecture: Mohammad Hassan Saleh Tabari: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing—original draft, Visualization. Fereshteh Khojastehmehr: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing—original draft. Günther H. Filz: Conceptualization, Writing—original draft, review & editing. (source: Tabari, M.H.S., Khojastehmehr, F. & Filz, G.H. A-T-G Louvers: a novel geometry and material driven spatial syntax for flexible structures. <i>Archit. Struct. Constr.</i> 5, 32 (2025). https://doi.org/10.1007/s44150-025-00150-6)
Biology:

Conceptualization: Caroline Vachias, Emilie Brasset, Vincent Mirouse. **Data curation:** Yoan Renaud. **Formal analysis:** Caroline Vachias, Vincent Mirouse. **Funding acquisition:** Vincent Mirouse. **Investigation:** Caroline Vachias, Camille Turlonias, Louis Grelée, Parvathy Venugopal, Vincent Mirouse. **Methodology:** Nathalie Gueguen, Parvathy Venugopal, Graziella Richard, Pierre Pouchin, Emilie Brasset. **Project administration:** Vincent Mirouse. **Software:** Pierre Pouchin. **Supervision:** Caroline Vachias, Emilie Brasset, Vincent Mirouse. **Visualization:** Yoan Renaud. **Writing – original draft:** Caroline Vachias, Vincent Mirouse» (source: *Vachias C, Turlonias C, Grelée L, Gueguen N, Renaud Y, Venugopal P, et al. (2025) Gap junctions allow transfer of metabolites between germ cells and somatic cells to promote germ cell growth in the Drosophila ovary. PLoS Biol 23(2): e3003045. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3003045>*)

Mechanical Engineering:

Fakhre Alam Khan: **Conceptualization; methodology; software resources; validation; formal analysis; resources; original draft; supervision.** Zahid Ullah: **Conceptualization; software resources; investigation; data curation; review and edit; data visualization; project administration.** Muhammad Aashan: **Conceptualization; methodology; validation; investigation; data curation; original draft.** Farooq Ahmad: **Conceptualization; software resources; validation; formal analysis; resources; original draft; data visualization.** Muhammad Saad: **Methodology; formal analysis; investigation; data curation; original draft.** Muhammad Azhar: **Methodology; formal analysis; resources; review and edit; data visualization.** Every contributor has thoroughly examined and endorsed the finalized manuscript for publication» (source: *Khan, F. A., Ullah, Z., Aashan, M., Ahmad, F., Saad, M., & Azhar, M. (2025). Life cycle assessment and energy efficiency of building façade materials: A case study of an educational building in Pakistan. The Journal of Engineering, 2025(1). <https://doi.org/10.1049/tje2.70047>*)

Additional references & resources:

UKRN Pilots working paper, <https://osf.io/qcgvk>

Nick Sheppard - Pilots 7 and 8 CRediT , <https://osf.io/tsbcy>

2. Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps

What: Researchers may use evidence synthesis techniques, such as systematic reviews, meta-analyses and scoping reviews, to comprehensively identify and assess the quality of the literature on a specific topic.

There are several types of evidence synthesis studies.

- **Systematic reviews** use clearly defined procedures to identify all studies that address a specific research question and assess the quality of those studies. When sufficient studies are found, researchers may pool the summary results of these studies to conduct a **meta-analysis** by assessing the size and direction of effects based all identified evidence, rather than drawing conclusions based on individual studies.
- **Individual patient meta-analyses** pool data on individuals from studies that have examined similar research questions to assess the size and direction of effects across studies. Individuals may include patients or participants for clinical studies, or animals for preclinical studies.
- **Scoping reviews** synthesize and map research on a topic, rather than assessing evidence on a narrow research question. Scoping reviews identify the nature, scope and extent of research on a particular topic and often include many different types of studies conducted using a wide range of methodological approaches.

When: Evidence synthesis should be performed in the beginning of a project or study, either to identify a research question from existing gaps in the literature, or to answer a research question already identified.

Why:

- Rigorously conducted evidence synthesis studies are a valuable tool for identifying research gaps.
- Evidence synthesis studies may be highly cited
- Early career researchers who conduct rigorous evidence synthesis studies learn to assess the quality of research in their field, which helps them to design better studies. They also strengthen their knowledge of existing evidence addressing their research question.
- Evidence synthesis studies can reduce waste by helping researchers to avoid design flaws found in previously published studies or preventing researchers from repeating research that has been performed many times before.

Examples:

- **Note:** Students should search the existing literature and preregistration platforms for evidence synthesis studies, such as PROSPERO, to confirm that an evidence synthesis study relevant to their research question hasn't already been conducted.

- **Note:** Students are encouraged to seek training in conducting evidence synthesis studies, preregister their study on PROSPERO and use reporting guidelines such as [PRISMA](#) or [MOOSE](#) when designing, conducting and reporting the evidence synthesis study.

3. Preregistration

What:

- A pre-registration is a time-stamped study protocol that the researchers deposit on a public repository before starting data collection. For quantitative studies, the pre-registration should include a detailed, complete data analysis plan.
- The protocol can be made public immediately, or it may be made public after an embargo period specified by the researchers (e.g. one year)
- Version control is used to update the study protocol – all modifications have a time stamp and can be explained in the manuscript (e.g., example of a [template](#) to report [Preregistration deviations](#))

When:

Why:

- A pre-registration allows transparent reporting of plans and hypothesis before data collection, and any modifications made to original plan. This enhances trustworthiness in research findings by protecting against [outcome switching](#), [p-hacking](#) and other [questionable research practices](#).
- A pre-registration provides a time stamp proving when you developed the idea and methodological plan
- A pre-registration makes it easier to detect selective reporting (only publishing results that confirm the hypothesis, or are statistically significant) and publication bias by listing all outcomes that you plan to measure
- A pre-registration allows students and supervisors to plan ahead, preventing design flaws

Examples - What might this look like?

Some fields rely on general registries. Other fields use registries that are designed for a particular field or study design.

General registries (across disciplines)	
OSF Registries, https://osf.io/registries - OSF offers different pre-registration templates. If there isn't a template that is more suitable for your study design, try using the AsPredicted template. This is designed to record the most essential pre-registration details.	AsPredicted, https://aspredicted.org/
Specific study types registries	
Systematic reviews: PROSPERO	Clinical trials: https://clinicaltrials.gov/ , https://clinicaltrials.eu/ , https://www.isrctn.com/
Field-specific (discipline-level) registries	
<p>Economics (Pre-analysis plans, PAPs) OSF Registries</p>	<p>Psychology OSF Registries Leibniz preregistration platform</p>

AEA RCT Registry (https://www.socialscienceregistry.org/)	
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Additional references & resources:

Alina Ladyzhensky, Amanda Staller, and Theresa Vo (August 19, 2025). White paper: Preregistration Essentials: Enhancing Transparency in Research. <https://osf.io/cp4x5>

Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7>

UKRN Pilots working paper, <https://osf.io/qcgvk>

4. Registered Reports

What: A journal reviews a study's introduction and methods before data collection starts, deciding whether to accept the paper based on the quality of the methods, instead of the attractiveness of the results.

In Stage 1, the journal peer reviews the study's planned methods. If the journal decides to issue a provisional acceptance, the researchers to start data collection. In Stage 2, the journal peer reviews the completed paper to confirm that the researchers followed the pre-specified methods, and all modifications were justified; and makes a final decision about acceptance.

Process:

- Authors design the study and submit an incomplete paper containing the introduction and methods to a journal that reviews registered reports.
- Peer reviewers review the introduction and methods before the study is conducted, focusing on the quality of the methods, and may request changes to the study design.
- The journal may provisionally accept the paper before data collection starts. A provisional acceptance means that the journal commits to publishing the results of the study, regardless of whether they confirm the hypothesis, if the authors follow the methods outlined in the registered report.
- The researchers perform the study, as specified in the registered report, and write the paper
- The journal reviews the completed paper once the study is completed, to confirm that the research team followed the methods specified in the registered report and any protocol deviations are justified.
- If accepted, the paper is published.

Why:

- Authors obtain reviewer feedback to correct study design and methodological flaws before starting the study. Students learn how to design robust studies.
- The decision to publish the study is based on the quality of the design, not whether the results are surprising or interesting.
- Students can obtain a provisional acceptance, confirming that their paper will be published before they start the study.
- By prespecifying the study plan, registered reports aim to avoid questionable research practices such as p-Hacking, HARKing or publication bias.
- Registered reports enhance the trustworthiness of research, which benefits researchers and non-academic stakeholders (e.g., industry can rely on more rigorous methods & findings when choosing objects for investment)

Cautionary note: When publishing a registered report, you can't start data collection until your protocol has been peer reviewed. This can be time-consuming and delay your research. One solution to this problem is to submit to Peer Communities In – [Registered Reports](#). This organization is designed to review registered reports. They allow you to schedule your submission date in

advance, and they will book reviewers who commit to reviewing your registered report within 2 weeks. [Peer Communities In – Registered Reports](#) partners with various journals, who commit to offering provisional acceptances if reviewers from Peer Communities In – Registered Reports decide that your registered report should be accepted. See the Peer Communities In – Registered Reports list of partner [journals](#).

Examples - What might this look like:

General information: Several journals now accept Registered Reports. You can find a list of participating journals from different fields on the following websites:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OSF resource: https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports (Participating journals) • Study resource (in OSF study repository): list of journals accepting RR and corresponding policies: https://osf.io/4sfww • Examples of RR studies linked in the RR Peer Community In (PCI) repository: https://rr.peercommunityin.org/ • Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7 		
Field-specific examples of Journals:		
Biology BMC Biology	Chemistry PeerJ Chemistry journals	Economics Journal of Development Economics; Oxford Open Economics
Neuroscience Cortex	Psychology Nature Human Behaviour	Sport Sciences Science & Medicine in Football journal

Additional references & resources:

Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7>

5. Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies

What: Researchers attempt to confirm the results of previously published studies by repeating a previously published study (reproducibility study) or using data and, if available, code from a previous study to determine whether they can replicate the results (replication study).

Why:

- Studies from psychology, biomedicine, and other fields have demonstrated that findings from many studies are not reproducible or replicable. Knowing which findings do, and don't, replicate, and under what conditions, is essential for researchers, policy-makers and other decision makers in many fields.
- Conducting a reproducibility or replication study helps early career researchers to identify problems that make it difficult to reproduce or replicate results. Researchers learn how to avoid these problems by improving the conduct and reporting of their own studies to improve reproducibility and replicability.
- Reproducibility and replication studies can provide important information about why studies aren't reproducible or don't replicate, which can lead to new insights and research directions.

Examples – what may this look like:

General information:	
• ...	
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Neuroscience</p> <p>Pavlov, Y. G., Adamian, N., Appelhoff, S., Arvaneh, M., Benwell, C. S. Y., Beste, C., Bland, A. R., Bradford, D. E., Bublitzky, F., Busch, N. A., Clayson, P. E., Cruse, D., Czeszumski, A., Dreber, A., Dumas, G., Ehinger, B., Ganis, G., He, X., Hinojosa, J. A., Huber-Huber, C., ... Mushtaq, F. (2021). #EEGManyLabs: Investigating the replicability of influential EEG experiments. <i>Cortex</i>; a journal devoted to the study of the nervous system and behavior, 144, 213–229. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2021.03.013</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Psychology</p> <p>Many Labs 2: Investigating Variation in Replicability Across Sample and Setting, https://osf.io/8cd4r/wiki/home/</p> <p>ManyBabies: collaborative project for replication and best practices in developmental psychology research, https://manybabies.org/publications/</p>

6. Open reusable step-by-step methods and protocols

What: Authors openly share or publish step-by-step protocols or detailed methods, describing how to perform a specific procedure. This allows others to reuse, adapt and modify the method to answer new research questions. Examples include posting a reusable step-by-step protocol on a public repository, publishing a reusable step-by-step protocol in a protocols journal, or publishing a methods paper describing and validating a new method.

Reusable step-by-step protocols offer detailed descriptions of the steps that researchers follow to implement a specific method. Step-by-step protocols should be very detailed, allowing researchers to implement the method successfully. Private protocols contained within electronic lab notebooks may be sufficiently detailed to allow others to implement the method but would need to be openly shared in a repository.

Please note: Study design protocols, which provide a detailed written plan for a specific study, are considered under Preregistration and Registered Reports.

Why:

- Methods are one of the most useful and reusable outputs that researchers create.
- Reproducibility starts with methods. We can't reproduce a study if we don't know what was done.
- Detailed methods are essential for responsible reuse of shared data. We can't reuse data responsibly without knowing how the data were generated.
- Sharing step-by-step protocols by publishing them or depositing them on a public repository allows others to reuse methods to replicate results or to answer new research questions.
- Researchers get credit for methods development work when others reuse and cite their methods.
- Well documented protocols make it easier to train new members of the research team and ensure that everyone is following the same procedures. They can also capture undocumented knowledge, which can be especially important in research groups with high turnover.
- Writing detailed study design protocols or reusable step-by-step protocols forces the researcher/student to organize, clarify and refine the elements of the study, enhancing scientific rigor and efficacy (Hulley, et al., 2013). Researchers also develop skills for documenting and clearly communicating complex procedures.
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in industry or academia can document their experience developing or implementing certain methods, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples - What might this look like?

General / Multidisciplinary:		
PLoS ONE and protocols.io, https://www.protocols.io/	Visual experiments protocols: JoVE, https://www.jove.com/	MethodsX , https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/methodsx

Field-specific examples:		
<p>Computational science</p> <p>Workflows, https://aiida-tutorials.readthedocs.io/en/latest/</p>	<p>Law</p> <p>Article defining relevant sources of legal information and search strategies, https://www.boomportaal.nl/tijdschrift/REM/lawandmethod-D-15-00005</p>	<p>Psychology + Health Sciences</p> <p>Journal: Trials, https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol + https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol/structured-study-protocol-template</p> <p>Journal: Clinical Trials, https://journals.sagepub.com/home/ctj</p>
	<p>Sport Sciences</p> <p>BMC Sports Science, Medicine and Rehabilitation, https://bmcsportsscimedrehabil.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol</p>	

7. Stakeholder engagement & Citizen Science

What: Citizen science or Stakeholder engagement are umbrella terms for methods that engage stakeholders in the research process (e.g., citizens, patients, industry, policymakers and regulators, etc.) as co-researchers or co-scientists. Participation can occur during any stage of the research lifecycle (e.g., development of research questions, definition of methods, data collection, data curation, etc).

‘Citizen science’ usually focuses involvement of society at large, whereas ‘Stakeholder engagement’ is the preferred term to describe the involvement of specific groups or communities (patients, industry, policymakers, regulators, etc).

Also known as: Participatory research; Community or Public engagement; Engaged Research Approach; Ethnographic research

Why:

- It increases the likelihood that the research will meet stakeholders’ needs, involving them in the knowledge production process (e.g. biomedicine: it brings patients associations to show students the perspective of patient’s lives)
- Research is undertaken in collaboration with the communities who are most likely affected by the research outcomes
- Given it aims to solve needs, it may attract funding directed to solve needs and priorities.
- Students develop skills in communication, collaboration, and project management by interacting with diverse stakeholders
- Stakeholders’ engagement as co-scientists contributes to scientific literacy of society at large

Examples - What might this look like?

Researchers may consult with patients, companies and employees to understand their needs, or involve communities in the co-production of research questions, methods, and materials. Researchers may also engage citizens or stakeholders in specific activities, such as using platforms with games for cell identification, asking people to transcribe documents, assign keywords and attribute classifications, or send photos with geolocation for mapping purposes.

You can find General information and projects:		
European Citizen Science Platform, https://eu-citizen.science/	Portuguese Citizen Science platform, https://www.cienciacidada.pt/	Citizen science projects, https://www.zooniverse.org/projects
Some field-specific examples:		
Anthropology (‘Ethnographic research’) Ethnographic research with visual media	Arts & Humanities Museology: engaging audience and visitors in museum governance and activities	Ecology and biodiversity Citizen Science e.g., https://invasoras.pt/
Economics & Business	Health: Preclinical research	History

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultation with companies and policy makers; • Business analysis and consultation with stakeholders to understand their needs 	Lalu, et al. 2024: Protocol for co-producing a framework and integrated resource platform for engaging patients in laboratory-based research.	<p>Creation of keywords and alternative descriptions, https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/juliegibb/stereoivision</p> <p>Historical research in Luxembourg, https://historesch.lu/en/contribute/</p>
<p>Physics, Astronomy and Space Sciences</p> <p>Solar Stormwatch CME catalogue – space weather citizen science project, https://doi.org/10.1002/2014SW001119</p>		

Additional references & resources:

UKRN Primer - Community Engagement in Research (Last edited: February 17, 2024), https://osf.io/preprints/osf/8jgxt_v1

Community engagement and involvement | NIHR, <https://www.nihr.ac.uk/research-funding/global-health/community-engagement-and-involvement>

8. Open/reusable resources/materials

What: Resources or materials that are used to conduct research and are shared in a repository, allowing other researchers to access and reuse the materials. Examples of resources and materials might include reagents, model organisms, educational materials, psychological tests, experimental tasks, tools, samples or curated documents. Resources and materials may be shared in an open repository, a restricted access repository with clearly specified procedures for accessing the materials (e.g., biobank; collection), or a commercial repository, depending on the type of material. Resources should have unique persistent identifiers (see practice below) to help others to determine exactly what resource was used.

Why:

- Sharing resources/materials allows others to reuse newly created resources/materials, increasing efficiency and accelerating discovery.
- Open materials save time and resources
- Researchers get credit for resource creation when others reuse and cite the resource
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in industry or academia that involve creation of materials can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples - How this may look like:

General examples:		
<p>General Research Resource Identification Portal, https://rrid.site/</p>		
Field-specific examples:		
<p>Arts & Humanities Museology: practical resources created from the collaborative research including toolkits (physical and digital), written guides, and online exhibitions (source UKRN Art & Design)</p>	<p>Anthropology Field notes, Sanjek, R. (Ed.) (1990). Fieldnotes: The makings of anthropology. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, https://archive.org/details/fieldnotes_making0000unse ; https://anthropod.net/2013/08/14/a-template-for-writing-fieldnotes/</p> <p>Collections</p>	
<p>Chemistry (Pharmaceutical Chemistry) Database of commercial-available compounds, https://zinc15.docking.org/</p> <p>ChemSpider: Search and Share Chemistry - Homepage</p>	<p>Psychology Open stimuli sets (OASIS, https://www.benedekkurdi.com/#!portfolio/project-4.html), Open experiments (https://pavlovia.org/), or Psychological test instruments available in REPOPSI, https://osf.io/5zb8p/ ; Open Test Arxiv, https://www.testarchiv.eu/</p>	<p>Health Sciences / Biology / Anthropology Samples and materials deposited in a biobank or repository (students do the deposit, filling the required files and detailing the metadata required to deposit).</p>

9. Unique identifiers for research materials and resources

What: Unique identifiers are ID numbers or codes assigned to research material to help researchers identify exactly what was used (like DOIs, but for research materials). Ideally this should be both globally and persistent identifiers. Examples include Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) for cell lines, antibodies, model organisms, plasmids, software and tools and core labs, or CAS numbers for chemicals.

What is not: Details like *catalog numbers, product numbers, version numbers, supplier names or equipment make and model information are not globally unique persistent identifiers*, as they are only identifiable *locally* (within a database or source). These details change over time as suppliers update their product portfolio and websites. Research studies have shown that many materials described in published papers cannot be identified from this information alone; hence, research communities have started developing unique persistent identifiers to create catalogs of lasting identification numbers for particular types of materials and resources.

Why

- Using unique persistent identifiers to specify exactly what was used improves transparency of research methods and increases reproducibility of methods and results
- Investigators always know what was used, even if the catalog number or supplier website changes, the supplier offers other new products that are similar, or the product is discontinued or sold to another supplier
- Some unique persistent identifier systems offer warnings about problematic materials. For example, the Research Resource Identifier (RRID) database gives warnings about cell lines that are known to be contaminated or misdiagnosed. Researchers can check materials for warnings before starting their study.
- **Added benefits for researchers who create resources:** Some unique persistent identifier systems, like RRIDs, allow researchers to create new persistent identifiers for resources that they create, “claim” these resources and add them to their ORCID profile. ORCIDs are unique persistent identifiers for researchers. Researchers who create new resources should include unique persistent identifiers in instructions on how to cite the resource. Having a unique persistent identifier makes it easier to cite a resource and quantify the impact of your work.

Examples – What might this look like?

Researchers should report unique persistent identifiers for items that have them in their manuscripts. Adding unique persistent identifiers to supply ordering lists for the research team makes it easy for everyone to order the right supplies and report correct identifiers in their manuscripts.

General:	
RRID (cell lines, antibodies, plasmids, model organisms like mice and rats, software and tools, core labs), https://www.rrids.org/	
Field-specific examples:	

Life Sciences	Arts and Humanities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical substances collection: CAS Registry, https://www.cas.org/cas-data/cas-registry • Proteins: UniProt, https://www.uniprot.org/ • The Identifiers.org Resolution Service provides consistent access to life science data (e.g. genes, parasites lifecycles, etc.) using Compact Identifiers (provides an assigned unique prefix and a local provider designated accession number (prefix:accession)), https://identifiers.org 	<p>Digital objects national registry (PT) (Registo Nacional de Objetos Digitais – RNOD), providing a persistent link, RNOD - Registo Nacional de Objectos Digitais</p>

Additional references & resources:

Plomp, E. (2020). Going Digital: Persistent Identifiers for Research Samples, Resources and Instruments. Data Science Journal, 19(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-046>

Bandrowski A, Brush M, Grethe JS et al. The Resource Identification Initiative: A cultural shift in publishing [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2015, 4:134 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.6555.2>)

FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

10. Open source code / Open software

What: Open-source software and code refers to sharing of software and code on a public repository with licenses that allow others to reuse, adapt and distribute the software or code; or to publish an open access software paper.

Why:

- Making code openly available allows others to implement computational methods, reproduce findings, or reuse code and software for new projects.
- Developing and making available open source code and software allows students to develop programming, debugging, documentation and collaborative skills, which are valuable skills in the job market. Students who share code and software document their experience, creating a portfolio that they can share with future employers.
- Researchers get credit for software and code development when others reuse and cite their code or software

Examples – What might this look like?

There are several general resources for sharing software and code:		
The R project for statistical computing, https://www.r-project.org ; researchers create and share packages, allowing others to perform particular types of analyses	GitHub, https://github.com/	Journal for Open software papers, https://joss.theoj.org/
Jupyter Notebooks, jupyter.org		
Field-specific examples:		
<p>Anthropology</p> <p><i>Ethnographic qualitative data statistical software – RQDA</i>, https://rqda.r-forge.r-project.org</p> <p><i>Forensic anthropology: 'JSDNE'</i>: A novel R package for estimating age quantitatively with the auricular surface by Dirichlet normal energy, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2024.106080 + https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/JSDNE/index.html</p>	<p>Computational materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computational materials: Open code and software, https://www.materialscloud.org/work/menu Virtual machine, https://quantum-mobile.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ 	<p>Economics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computational Economic models, https://github.com/OpenSourceEconomics • Quantitative economic modelling, https://github.com/QuantEcon • Reproducible workflows, https://lachlandeer.github.io/snake-make-econ-r-tutorial/ <p>Operations research / management science: Algorithms</p>
<p>Law</p> <p>Legal Text Mining resources, https://github.com/Liquid-Legal-Institute/Legal-Text-Analytics ; https://liquid-legal-institute.com/workinggroups/legal-text-analytics/</p>	<p>Neuroscience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fMRIprep, Reproducible workflows for preprocessing of data, https://fmripred.org/en/stable/ 	<p>Psychology</p> <p>Open-source software for cognitive and behavioral experiments, PsychoPy, https://www.psychopy.org/ ; LabsJS, https://lab.js.org/</p>

<p>Social Sciences NetLogo Models, https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/models/</p>	<p>Engineering OpenFOAM (from complex fluid flows involving chemical reactions, turbulence and heat transfer, to acoustics, solid mechanics and electromagnetics), https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/overview</p>	<p>Social and Behavioral Sciences Implicit Association Test (Harvard), -programming language (JS): https://minnojs.github.io/docs/start/ -study materials (pictures, etc): https://www.projectimplicit.net/resources/study-materials/</p>
<p>Computer science Platform to save data and models - https://www.openml.org/</p>	<p>Healthcare Models: open source simulation tools; https://youtu.be/nytslQOjumI?feature=shared</p>	<p>Physics, Astronomy and Space Science Open source models, https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/100589/3/OpenResearchCaseStudy-2021-Barnard.pdf</p>
<p>Environment, Agriculture, Decision science TAMSAT-ALERT, https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/86472/1/OpenResearchCaseStudy-2019-Black.pdf ; https://github.com/tamsat-alert/v1-0</p>		

Additional resources & references:

Turner, A., Topor, M., Stewart, A. J., Owen, N., Kenny, A. R., Jones, A. L., & Ellis, D. A. (2020, October 30). Open Code and Software: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qw9ck>

11. Open hardware

What: Open source hardware refers to making design specifications for a physical object available, with a license that allows anyone to study, create, modify, and distribute the object.

Why:

- Open hardware allows others to construct a given object and share their knowledge of hardware design and function.
- Students gain practical engineering and design skills while learning about cost-effective, scalable solutions. This hands-on experience is highly marketable in tech-driven industries.
- Both academic and external stakeholders (e.g., industry) can reuse and adapt open hardware designs to prototype and develop products; this can provide feasible solutions for lower income countries
- Researchers get credit for hardware development when others reuse and cite the resource

Examples – What might this may look like?

Health Sciences	Engineering
Audiology, A4A, https://www.cisuc.uc.pt/en/projects/a4a-audiology-for-all (available at platform evollu, https://www.evollu.com/ecossistema/) Microscopy, https://openflexure.org/ Prosthetic open limbs, e-NABLE, https://enablingthefuture.org / Ventilators – OpenLung, https://gitlab.com/open-source-ventilator/	Electronic engineering – wireless communication, Reference Development Kit (RDK), https://myriadrf.org , Satellites, https://satnogs.org

12. Open benchmarking of problems

What: A benchmark is a standardized validation framework that allows for a direct comparison of the prediction accuracy of various models that address the same research problem (Pankowska et al., 2024).

Why:

- there is an increasing need to continuously evaluate which methods (e.g., algorithms) performs best in which context to inform best practices (Luecken et al, 2024)

Examples - What might this look like?

General:	
Götz, M., Sarma, A., & O'Boyle, E. H. (2024). The multiverse of universes: A tutorial to plan, execute and interpret multiverses analyses using the R package multiverse. <i>International journal of psychology : Journal international de psychologie</i> , 59(6), 1003–1014. https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.13229	
Field-specific examples:	
Biology/Computational Biology and Bioinformatics - Open Problems in Single-cell analysis, https://openproblems.bio/results , Luecken et al. (2024). https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4181617/v1	Social Sciences Benchmarking Challenges, Pankowska, P., Mendrik, A., Emery, T., & Garcia-Bernardo, J. (2024). The potential of benchmark challenges in the social sciences. <i>Social Science Information</i> , 63(4), 498-519. https://doi.org/10.1177/05390184241297742
Computational science -Optimization of algorithms, Bartz-Beielstein et al. (2020). https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.03488 ;	Mathematics FrontierMath, Galzer et al. (2024), https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.04872v5
Neuroscience Comparison of different analytical approaches: Yücel et al, 2025, https://osf.io/preprints/metaarxiv/pc6x8_v1 , https://openfnirs.org/data/fresh/ Multiverse analysis in neuroimaging: Dafflon, J., F. Da Costa, P., Váša, F. et al. A guided multiverse study of neuroimaging analyses. <i>Nat Commun</i> 13, 3758 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31347-8	

Additional references & resources:

Pankowska, P., Mendrik, A., Emery, T., & Garcia-Bernardo, J. (2024). The potential of benchmark challenges in the social sciences. *Social Science Information*, 63(4), 498-519.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/05390184241297742> (Original work published 2024)

Malte Luecken, Scott Gigante, Daniel Burkhardt et al. Defining and benchmarking open problems in single-cell analysis, 03 April 2024, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square
[\[https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4181617/v1\]](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4181617/v1)

13. Data sharing (FAIR; Open)

What: Research data are shared in a repository, ideally in a way that makes them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Depending on the type of data, data may be shared on an open repository or a restricted access repository. For responsible and proper data reuse either by humans or machines, documentation and contextualization (known as *metadata*) should always be provided with data. Metadata may include information such as study description, methods used, data types, licensing, access and reuse conditions.

Openness and FAIRness (FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) of data mean different things and relate to different practices. Data can be open while not being FAIR, and data can be FAIR while not being openly accessible.

- **Open data sharing:** Data that is not sensitive may be shared in an open access repository. Open data must be accompanied by detailed metadata, which provide information about what the dataset is and how the data were collected. High quality metadata is essential for responsible data reuse.
- **Restricted access data sharing:** Sensitive data may be shared on a restricted access repository, where potential users need to apply or agree to adhere to certain conditions to access the data. Archiving data on a restricted access repository ensures that a clean, reusable version of the dataset is stored in a findable location with a long-term preservation strategy. Procedures for accessing restricted access data should be clearly specified (e.g. who to contact, what forms or paperwork should be completed to access the data, conditions for reuse). Data shared on restricted access repositories should include high quality metadata to facilitate responsible data reuse. If possible, sensitive data can still be openly shared as [synthetic data](#): «[Synthetic datasets mimic real datasets by preserving their statistical properties and the relationships between variables. Importantly, this method also reduces disclosure risk to essentially nil as no record in the synthetic dataset represents a real individual.](#)»
- **Metadata sharing:** When data cannot be shared on an open access or restricted access repository, researchers may still share open metadata describing contextual information about the dataset and methods used to collect the data. This helps others to find the dataset and initiate collaborations.

Cautionary note: *Data sharing requires sound data management to ensure data quality.*

Researchers who are interested in sharing data should create a data management plan when designing the study, to address considerations such as ethical requirements, use of standards for (meta)data, documentation, storage, access and security of data.

Why:

- Sharing of data and connected properly described metadata allows others to reproduce findings, reuse data for evidence synthesis or to answer new research questions. Access to metadata allows others to find relevant studies and datasets, even when the data is not fully open.

- Students learn robust data management and curation skills, including metadata standards and data sharing protocols, which are increasingly valuable in academia and non-academic environments
- Both academic and external stakeholders can access large, high-quality datasets to inform their R&D activities, accelerating discovery and potentiating research-based innovation
- Researchers get credit for data generation when others reuse and cite their data

Examples – Where can I share data?

General repositories for data sharing:		
Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ ; Dryad, https://datadryad.org/ ; Figshare, https://figshare.com/ ; OECD, https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets.html ; OSF (research data deposited within project folders), https://osf.io/ ;	PT government: https://dados.gov.pt/pt/datasets/	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (or EUDAT CDI) is an infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe, https://eudat.eu/
Institutional repositories ‘open/FAIR (meta)data’ for data sharing:		
Dataverse research data repositories, check institutional repositories at https://dataverse.org	Open access: DataShare (UnivEdinburgh), https://datashare.ed.ac.uk/ ; MADA (Univ Manheim), https://madata.bib.uni-mannheim.de/	Restricted access: DataVault (Univ Edinburgh), https://digitalresearchservices.ed.ac.uk/resources/data-vault ; Data Cube (Univ Manheim), https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/en/teaching-and-research/research-data-center-fdz/services-of-the-fdz/sharing-data-in-a-secure-environment/
CERN, https://opendata.cern.ch/		
Field-specific repositories ‘open/FAIR (meta)data’ where to find datasets:		
Health and Social care DataLoch (Univ Edinburgh), https://dataloch.org/	Neuroscience OpenNeuro, https://openneuro.org/ , NeuroVault, https://neurovault.org/	Social sciences Qualitative data, https://qdr.syr.edu/
Pharmacology, Pharmaceuticals Briggs, et al. (2021). Guidelines for FAIR sharing of preclinical safety and off-target pharmacology data. ALTEX, 38(2), 187–197. https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2011181	Physics CERN, https://opendata.cern.ch/	Health Sciences YODA, restricted access repository for sharing clinical data, https://yoda.yale.edu/
Psychology, Medicine Release of synthetic data (using synthpop.R package), https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53275	Humanities Journal of Open Humanities Data, https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/	

<p>Major-Smith D, Kwong ASF, Timpson NJ et al. Releasing synthetic data from the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC): Guidelines and applied examples [version 2; peer review: 3 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Res 2024, 9:57 (https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.20530.2)</p>	<p>Law: data collection may consider people, countries, but also texts inspection and interpretation (https://guides.ll.georgetown.edu/c.php?g=365532&p=7886015; https://libguides.vermontlaw.edu/EmpiricalLegal/data; https://hls.harvard.edu/library/research-services/legal-databases/)</p>	
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Additional references & resources:

Daniel S Quintana (2020) A synthetic dataset primer for the biobehavioural sciences to promote reproducibility and hypothesis generation eLife 9:e53275. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53275>

Towse, J. N., Rumsey, S., Owen, N., Langford, P., Jaquiere, M., & Bolibaugh, C. (2020, October 30). Data Sharing: a Primer from UKRN. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wp4zu_v1

UKRN resource: Open Research Indicators UKRN working paper 230619, <https://osf.io/qcgvk>

Towse, J. N., Rumsey, S., Owen, N., Langford, P., Jaquiere, M., & Bolibaugh, C. (2020, October 30). Data Sharing: a Primer from UKRN. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wp4zu_v1

14. Follow Reporting Guidelines

What: Study design and reporting guidelines are recommended, consensus-based, community accepted standards that specify essential details that authors should report for specific types of studies to ensure transparency, robustness and reproducibility. Reporting guidelines may include checklists, flow diagrams, or structured text to guide authors in reporting necessary elements. Guidelines are generally designed for specific study designs or research methods.

Reporting guidelines are very common in the biomedical sciences and psychology but may be less common in other fields.

Why:

- Facilitates accurate, complete, and transparent reporting of research studies to improve research reproducibility and usefulness.
- Students gain skills in good research practices, by using standard recommendations to guide study design and reporting
- Many journals require authors to adhere to reporting guidelines. Ensuring that you collect all necessary information when designing your study reduces the likelihood that your paper will be rejected for missing information. Using a reporting guideline to write your paper reduces the likelihood that reviewers or editors will return your paper due to missing information, or that you will need to add additional details during revision or initial manuscript checks.

Cautionary note: Researchers should also look for study design guidelines for their study type. Study design guidelines help authors to address critical considerations when designing their study. Examples include the PREPARE guideline for preclinical animal research and the SPIRIT guideline for clinical trials.

Examples - How this may look like:

General examples:	
Sex and Gender in Research (SAGER Guidelines), Heidari et al. Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use. Res Integr Peer Rev 1, 2 (2016). https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-016-0007-6	Reporting Checklist for patient & public engagement: Staniszewska, S., Brett, J., Simeria, I., Seers, K., Mockford, C., Goodlad, S. et al. (2017). GRIPP2 reporting checklists: tools to improve reporting of patient and public involvement in research. BMJ 358:j3453. doi:10.1136/bmj.j3453
Systematic reviews meta-analysis, PRISMA, https://www.prisma-statement.org/	
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Health Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equator network (collection of guidelines – check for guidelines for your study design type), https://www.equator-network.org/ 	<p style="text-align: center;">Neurosciences</p> <p>COBIDAS, https://www.equator-network.org/reporting-guidelines-keyword/cobidas/ ;</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epidemiology: STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE), https://www.strobe-statement.org/ • Clinical trials: CONSORT for randomized controlled trials, TREND for non-randomized trials; COMET, standardized sets of outcomes (“Core Outcome Sets”, COS) • Animal pre-clinical studies, ARRIVE, https://arriveguidelines.org/ • Smith AJ, Clutton RE, Lilley E, Hansen KEA, Brattelid T. PREPARE: guidelines for planning animal research and testing. <i>Laboratory Animals</i>. 2017;52(2):135-141. doi:10.1177/0023677217724823 	<p>cred-nf - https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32176800/;</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Psychology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPIRIT, https://www.goodreports.org/reporting-checklists/spirit/, • Methodology: Quality assessment (forms) 	

15. Preprints

What: Preprints refer to research papers that are posted on an open public server prior to peer review. Authors can post updated versions as they improve and refine the paper.

Why:

- Authors can get feedback and improve the paper before it is published. Preprints can be shared with a wider audience than the small number of reviewers who examine the paper during journal peer review.
- Papers that are first posted as preprints start accumulating citations sooner, as others have already seen and started citing preprints by the time that they are published. The preprint website typically provides a link to the published version once the paper is published in a peer reviewed journal.
- Funders increasingly allow authors to list preprints in funding applications. This is particularly valuable for early-stage researchers and others who want to show evidence of their work. Preprints can be posted within a few days, whereas peer review and publication are time consuming and may not be completed in time for a grant application deadline.
- Authors get scooping protection, as the time-stamped preprint clearly shows when the research team first posted their paper.
- Students can make their studies and outputs visible earlier, allowing for networking opportunities, and providing early career recognition.

Examples – Where can I post preprints?

General examples and where to find preprint repositories:	
Reviews and Other types of papers: https://osf.io/preprints	All types of studies: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_preprint_repositories
Field specific preprint repositories:	
Anthropology Preprints may be referred to as working paper series, https://anthropology.utk.edu/opportunities/working-paper-series/	Physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics ArXiv, https://arxiv.org/ (original preprint repository)
Biology and life sciences bioRxiv (original research only), https://www.biorxiv.org/ Case study: Quantitative Biology > Genomics, a preprint that is not published in a journal but it is vital to the genomics field, https://arxiv.org/abs/1303.3997	Chemistry ChemRxiv, https://chemrxiv.org/engage/chemrxiv/public-dashboard
Information Science e-prints in Library and Information science, http://eprints.rclis.org/	Law Bepress Legal Repository – offers working papers and preprints, https://law.bepress.com/
Medicine MedRxiv (original research only; Preprints are preliminary reports of work that have not been	Psychology PsyArXiv, https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv

certified by peer review. They should not be relied on to guide clinical practice or health-related behavior and should not be reported in news media as established information) https://www.medrxiv.org/	
Social Sciences socArXiv, https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv	Sports sciences SportRxiv, https://sportrxiv.org/index.php/server
Economics SSRN, https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en/ern/	

Additional references & resources:

Spitschan, M., Rumsey, S., Jaquiere, M., & Galizzi, M. M. (2020, October 30). Preprints: a Primer from UKRN.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m4zyh>

16. Reporting of null results

What: Researchers report studies and results that don't support their hypotheses, i.e., report of (true) negative or null findings, following the analytical test of a hypothesis. When reporting studies with mixed (i.e., both positive and negative) results, researchers report all results obtained during a study, including those that aren't statistically significant or don't support their hypotheses.

While the practices on this list focus on the report at the thesis level, students are also strongly encouraged to publish null results to avoid selective reporting and publication bias in the research literature.

Why:

- Research projects should result in the potential for the transfer of the new knowledge, allowing other researchers to reproduce the results (as part of their own research or for evaluation purposes). This includes research activities that have negative results (e.g., an initial hypothesis fails to be confirmed or a product cannot be developed as originally intended). If one aims to produce new knowledge, the results cannot remain tacit (i.e. remain solely in the minds of the researchers), as they, and the associated knowledge, would be at risk of being lost (OECD, 2015, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>).
- Reporting of null results reduces biases in the research literature and avoids the questionable research practices of selective reporting, publication bias and HARKing.
 - **Selective reporting:** Researchers only report the data or outcome variables that supported their hypothesis or were statistically significant in their research paper and omit other outcome variables that did not support their hypothesis or were not statistically significant.
 - **Publication bias (towards positive results):** Researchers don't publish or report studies that have negative or null results or don't support the researchers' hypothesis. To prevent positive publication bias, which leads to inaccurate effect sizes, both (true) positive and (true) negative findings need to be reported. This will provide an accurate representation of the research field, rather than focusing merely on surprising or novel findings (Schweinfurth et al, 2024).
 - **HARKing (“Hypothesizing After Results are Known”):** In confirmatory studies, researchers present a *post hoc* hypothesis (i.e., one that is actually based on or informed by one's results) as if it were an *a priori* (i.e., before testing and knowing results) hypotheses (Kerr, 1998, https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr0203_4), reframing their hypotheses to create a more compelling narrative. This often includes emphasizing statistically significant, interesting or surprising fundings, and omitting null findings.
Selective reporting, publication bias and HARKing distort the evidence base that researchers, policy makers and others use to plan future studies and make decisions. Relying on a biased and distorted evidence base can increase research waste and lead to flawed decisions that harm the intended beneficiaries of research.

- Reporting of null results reduces research waste, as others are less likely to attempt similar studies.

Examples:

- The Missing Pieces: A Collection of Negative, Null and Inconclusive Results, <https://collections.plos.org/collection/missing-pieces/>
- Hornig M, Briese T, Buie T, Bauman ML, Lauwers G, Siemetzki U, et al. (2008) Lack of Association between Measles Virus Vaccine and Autism with Enteropathy: A Case-Control Study. PLoS ONE 3(9): e3140. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0003140>

Additional References & Resources:

Bik E. M. (2024). Publishing negative results is good for science. *Access microbiology*, 6(4), 000792. <https://doi.org/10.1099/acmi.0.000792>

Clark, A. (2017). Negative results: A crucial piece of the scientific puzzle. *EveryONE*. <https://everyone.plos.org/2017/10/26/negative-results-a-crucial-piece-of-the-scientific-puzzle/>

OECD (2015), Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>

Mlinarić, A., Horvat, M., & Šupak Smolčić, V. (2017). Dealing with the positive publication bias: Why you should really publish your negative results. *Biochemia medica*, 27(3), 030201. <https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2017.030201>

Schweinfurth, M. K., & Frommen, J. G. (2024). Beyond the null: Recognizing and reporting true negative findings. *iScience*, 28(1), 111676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.111676>

17. Science communication & Policy recommendations

What:

- Science communication is a research dissemination and outreach activity in which researchers, science communicators and journalists share materials, activities or results of research projects with different publics in plain language. They may offer concise or more comprehensive analyses, along with recommendations to inform policymakers, academics, practitioners, or the public.
- Defined as organized, explicit, and intended actions that aim to communicate scientific knowledge, methodology, processes, or practices in settings where non-scientists are a recognized part of the audience (Horst, Davies, & Irwin (2017, p.884)).
- An umbrella term covering a wide variety of activities, including professional communication by scientists; interactions between scientists and members of the public; the media representation of science; and the ways people use scientific knowledge in their own lives (Mellor & Webster, 2017, p.1).
- Currently, it employs the Public participation paradigm (leaving behind the simple Dissemination paradigm), aiming an open dialogue and deliberation between the public, experts and decision makers (Kappel K and Holmen SJ, 2019).

Also known as: Science dissemination and Outreach, Knowledge exchange with stakeholders; Public engagement (although different from Stakeholder Engagement) aiming

Why:

- General public and non-academic stakeholders have facilitated access to the knowledge produced by the use of plain language and adequate dissemination methods for the target public
- Raises scientific literacy of different groups of stakeholders in society
- Increasing the relevance of the research
- Increasing recruitment to clinical or social research
- Improving the design of the research to address ethical concerns, improve the research tools and make it easier for the people taking part
- Improving the quality of the data and its interpretation
- Making it more likely that the findings of the research will be used to make a difference to service users' lives.
- Science communication improves scientific/research literacy and allows the public to interact and benefit from research, facilitating translation of research results to policies
- Students gain skills in writing, abstracting and translating research jargon, pitch and communication. These skills may be highly valuable in the job market.
- Students who are seeking jobs in industry, education or academia that involve science communication can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples - What might this look like?

Science communication may take many formats and be target for different publics. It can refer to competitions to pitch your research in simple language and very short time; talks and round tables for broader audiences; informal talks at public spaces (e.g., bar), production of materials to be disseminated in social media (e.g., newspapers, etc) or through dedicated pages and websites; or get more formal structures and purposes such as policy briefs and laws summarized into simpler language.

General examples:	
Competitions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FameLab, https://www.cheltenhamfestivals.org/our-projects/famelab/famelab-international , ○ 3MT (3-minute thesis competition), https://threeminutethesis.uq.edu.au/ ○ ScienceSlam, https://www.scienceslam.de/ ○ Falling Walls Lab (innovative ideas), https://falling-walls.com/lab 	Informal talks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PubhD ○ Pint of Science ○ Soapbox Science ○ Podcasts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lay Summaries: https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides/write-lay-summary 	Digital objects and resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Games ● Graphical abstracts ● Infographics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Media and social media 	Participation in big and general events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Researchers' Night ● Science Fairs and Festivals ● Participation in exhibitions, and speed dating, ● Theatre plays, ● Visits to schools and other institutions
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Arts & Humanities</p> -Cultural heritage, Europeana, https://www.europeana.eu/en , https://humanitiesdata.com/resources/284 -Museology: interactive websites including images of objects, diagrams, and descriptions of research processes (source: UKRN Art & Design); -Museums: https://journal.sciencemuseum.ac.uk/article/the-research-museum-a-place-of-integrated-knowledge-production/#abstract	<p style="text-align: center;">Chemistry</p> Chemistry World, https://www.chemistryworld.com
<p style="text-align: center;">Health Sciences</p> -EuroHuntington, https://eurohuntington.org/news/ -Clinical trials: Cochrane Dissemination Checklist, https://training.cochrane.org/online-learning/knowledge-translation/how-share-cochrane-evidence/dissemination-essentials-checklist	<p style="text-align: center;">Neuroscience</p> Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian Museum, https://gulbenkian.pt/cerebro-mais-vasto-que-o-ceu/
Physics	Law

<p>Youtube channel MinutePhysics, https://www.youtube.com/@MinutePhysics</p>	<p>UCL; Faculty of Laws, Policy Briefs, https://www.ucl.ac.uk/laws/research/making-impact/shaping-world-through-impactful-research/policy-briefs World Justice Project, https://worldjusticeproject.org/our-work/publications/policy-briefs</p>
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18. Open Educational resources

What: Open educational resources are digital or printed teaching, learning, and research materials that are in the public domain or have been released under an open license that allows no-cost access, use adaptation, redistribution by others with limited or no restrictions (<https://guides.library.harvard.edu/OER>).

Why:

- Making educational resources openly available reduces barriers in access to education and educational materials.
- Instructors can reuse and adapt these materials for teaching in other settings.
- Researchers who share open educational materials may expand their networks, develop collaborations, and build their professional reputation among students and instructors when others reuse these materials.
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in education, higher education or academia can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples – What might this look like?

General examples:	
FORRT, https://forrt.org/ ;	OSSCAR (Open Software Services for Classrooms and Research), https://www.osscar.org/
Research Integrity: Embassy of Good Science, https://embassy.science/wiki/Main_Page	
Field-specific examples:	
Neuroscience Simply neuroscience, https://www.simplyneuroscience.org/	

Practices that were considered but are not currently in the list

- Thesis proposals project *[must meet the criteria for Preregistration]*
- Research data management plan (DMP) *[will be used as path towards Data sharing]*
- Open Access
- Open Innovation
- Open Repositories
- Open to Other Knowledge Systems
- Positionality statements (or researcher reflexivity)
- Ontological and epistemological assumptions
- Conflicts of interest